

Cure Kinetics of a Transesterification-type Vitrimers derived from a Commercial Epoxy-Anhydride Thermoset

Joshua Ilse, Pascal Hubert

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Structures & Composite
Materials Laboratory

Research Center for High Performance
Polymer and Composite Systems

Surveying Circularity in the Composites Industry

Composite Waste Management

→ Only 4% of composites are recycled

Market by volume

→ How can we make future composites more recyclable?

- Reuse
- Repurpose
- Recycling
- Energy Recovery
- Disposal

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Vitrimers

- Reuse
- Repurpose
- Recycling
- Energy Recovery
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Methodology – Leverage Pre-Existing Materials & Processes

Table 1: Mix ratio (by weight).

	Resin (R)	Hardener (H)	Accelerator (A)	Vitrimer Catalyst (VC)
Thermoset	100	90	3	-
Vitrimer	100	45	3	14

“Vitrimerization” of Commercial Thermoset

Objectives

Prior work: *is there vitrimer behaviour?*

Cure Cycle
4 h @ 80 °C
+ 4 h @ 140 °C

$$\tau(T) = \tau_0 \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)$$

Characteristic Relaxation Time

This work: *how does cure behaviour change?*

- Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)
 - Uncured resin (Thermoset/Vitrimer)
 - Isothermals: 80, 90, 100, 110, 120 °C
- Phenomenological model-fitting approach to cure kinetics:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)_i f(\alpha)_i$$

Reaction
Rate

Rate
Constant

Reaction
Model

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Results – Thermoset

Heat Flow vs. Time

Conversion vs. Time

Reaction Rate vs. Conversion

$$[1] \Delta H_{tot} = \Delta H_{rxn} + \Delta H_{res}$$

ΔH_{tot} : Total Heat of Reaction

ΔH_{rxn} : Heat of Reaction

ΔH_{res} : Residual Heat of Reaction

$$[2] \alpha(t) = \frac{\int_0^t \frac{dH}{dt}}{\Delta H_{tot}} = \frac{\Delta H_t}{\Delta H_{tot}}$$

H_t : Heat of Reaction at time t

$$[3] \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{dH/dt}{\Delta H_{Tot}}$$

Results – Thermoset

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)f(\alpha)$$

Reaction
Rate

Rate
Constant

Reaction
Model

→ Single-step reaction

Autocatalytic:

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m(1 - \alpha)^n$$

Arrhenius:

$$k(T) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \alpha^m(1 - \alpha)^n$$

→ 4 unknowns: A, E_a, m, n

$$\ln A = 19.20 \text{ [1/s]}$$

$$E_a = 76.91 \text{ [kJ/mol]}$$

$$m = 0.6236 \text{ [-]}$$

$$n = 1.8208 \text{ [-]}$$

Results – Thermoset

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)f(\alpha)$$

Reaction
Rate

Rate
Constant

Reaction
Model

→ Single-step reaction, 0 – 0.7 conversion

Autocatalytic:

Arrhenius:

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m(1 - \alpha)^n$$

$$k(T) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \alpha^m(1 - \alpha)^n$$

→ 4 unknowns: A, E_a, m, n

$$\ln A = 16.73 \text{ [1/s]}$$

$$E_a = 72.43 \text{ [kJ/mol]}$$

$$m = 0.2406 \text{ [-]}$$

$$n = 0.7551 \text{ [-]}$$

Results – Vitrimers

Heat Flow vs. Time

Conversion vs. Time

Reaction Rate vs. Conversion

$$[1] \Delta H_{tot} = \Delta H_{rxn} + \Delta H_{res}$$

ΔH_{tot} : Total Heat of Reaction

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$$[2] \alpha(t) = \frac{\int_0^t \frac{dH}{dt}}{\Delta H_{tot}} = \frac{\Delta H_t}{\Delta H_{tot}}$$

H_t : Heat of Reaction at time t

$$[3] \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{dH/dt}{\Delta H_{Tot}}$$

Results – Vitrimer

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)_i f(\alpha)_i \quad ; i = 2$$

Reaction
Rate

Rate
Constant

Reaction
Model

Autocatalytic:

$$f(\alpha)_{1,2} = \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n$$

Arrhenius:

$$k(T) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a1}}{RT}\right) \alpha^{m_1} (1 - \alpha)^{n_1} + A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a2}}{RT}\right) \alpha^{m_2} (1 - \alpha)^{n_2}$$

→ 8 unknowns: $A_1, E_{a1}, m_1, n_1, A_2, E_{a2}, m_2, n_2$

$$\begin{aligned} \ln A_1 &= 18.17 \text{ [1/s]} & \ln A_2 &= 34.92 \text{ [1/s]} \\ E_{a1} &= 79.42 \text{ [kJ/mol]} & E_{a2} &= 121.5 \text{ [kJ/mol]} \\ m_1 &= 0.02399 \text{ [-]} & m_2 &= 8.157 \text{ [-]} \\ n_1 &= 2.33 \text{ [-]} & n_2 &= 2.883 \text{ [-]} \end{aligned}$$

Summary – Thermoset vs. Vitrimer 3D Model-Fit

Thermoset

Vitrimer

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Thank you

Questions?

Contact:

joshua.ilse@mail.mcgill.ca

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